

D3ADVERT: DATA-DRIVEN DECISION MAKING FOR AD PERSONALIZATION THROUGH PERSONALITY ANALYSIS USING BILSTM NETWORK

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ABSTRACT

Personalized advertising holds greater potential for higher conversion rates compared to generic advertisements. However, its widespread application in the retail industry faces challenges due to complex implementation processes. These complexities impede the swift adoption of personalized advertisement on a large scale. Personalized advertisement, being a data-driven approach, necessitates consumer-related data, adding to its complexity. This paper introduces an innovative data-driven decision-making framework, D3Advert, which personalizes advertisements by analyzing personalities using a BiLSTM network. The framework utilizes the Myers–Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI) dataset for development. The employed BiLSTM network, specifically designed and optimized for D3Advert, classifies user personalities into one of the sixteen MBTI categories based on their social media posts. The classification accuracy is 86.42%, with precision, recall, and F1-Score values of 85.11%, 84.14%, and 83.89%, respectively. The D3Advert framework personalizes advertisements based on these personality classifications. Experimental implementation and performance analysis of D3Advert demonstrate a 40% improvement in impression. D3Advert's innovative and straightforward approach has the potential to transform personalized advertising and foster widespread adoption of personalized advertisement in marketing.

Keywords: Personalized advertisement, Deep Learning, MBTI Dataset, BiLSTM Network, NLP.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Personalized advertisement is more engaging and effective than generalized advertisement [1]. However, the complex nature of human psychology imposes a challenge in advertisement personalization [2]. Today's social media platforms have become places to share thoughts and feelings and express opinions. As a result, social media posts reveal the psychological types of the users. This paper utilizes the intrinsic sentiments of social media posts to predict the psychology type of the users using a Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (BiLSTM) network [3]. The prediction is further utilized to personalize advertisements. It is an innovative approach of combining the sentiment of social media posts with Deep Learning (DL) technology to predict the type of psychology of the users and increase the effectiveness of advertisements by personalizing them according to the prediction.

A unique BiLSTM network optimized for learning from The Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI) dataset and predicting the psychology types has been developed in this paper. The challenges of processing the MBTI dataset and converting it into vectors while handling the variable length issues have been overcome in this paper. As a result, the BiLSTM network gains the capability of processing 1500 tokens at a time and predicting the MBTI types accurately. Moreover, the personality classifier developed in this paper has been experimented with in a real-world-like test environment, demonstrating that it effectively increases the advertisement impression. The unique contributions of this paper are listed below.

- Effective application of BiLSTM network in developing data-driven decision-making system for advertisement personalization.
- Improving the advertisement impression rate by 40%.
- Gaining an impressive accuracy of 86.42% with 85.11% precision, 84.14% recall, and 83.89% F1-score.

The remainder of the paper is structured into six distinct sections. The second section discusses pertinent research. The methodology behind the proposed D3Advert is detailed in the third section. The fourth section focuses on the experimental results and their evaluation. Subsequently, the limitations and future scopes of the proposed system are examined in the fifth section. The paper concludes with the sixth section.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The review by H. Ahmad et al. [4] suggests that the personality trait classification from the textual content is a vibrant research field. The study by A. S. Khan et al. [5] agrees with this statement and further highlights the effectiveness of the MBTI dataset for personality classification. According to K. N. P. Kumar et al., [6], as the MBTI dataset consists of social media posts, it reflects the unbiased sentiment of the users. N. Cerkez et al. [7] also agree with this statement. That is why the MBTI dataset has been selected to develop the proposed D3Advert system.

Machine Learning approaches to classify personality traits from the MBTI dataset is a well-developed research branch [8]. The sentiment-aware deep learning approach for personality detection system developed by Z. Ren et al. [9] shows the effectiveness of DL algorithms in this field. S. Ontoum et al. [10], S. Biswas [11], K. Kim et al. [12], and M. Maulidah [13] and many others applied DL algorithms on the same purpose. However, most research focuses on developing classifiers that ignore the application domain [11]. The proposed D3Advert fills the gap by developing and applying a unique personality classifier to advertisement personalization.

A. Bleier et al. studied the effectiveness of personalized advertisement [14]. H. A. Monem et al. [15] also explored the same field. According to them, it is an effective but challenging field [16]. The variety of consumers has made advertisement personalization challenging [17]. B. Gao et al. [18] studied these challenges from the Artificial Intelligence (AI) point of view. However, they didn't address an effective way to overcome the challenges. This paper proposed an effective solution to this problem, which demonstrates the potential to revolutionize advertisement personalization using Deep Learning technology.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Dataset Analysis and Processing

The dataset analysis involves inspecting the structure of the dataset, studying the metadata, and understanding the dataset structure [19]. The dataset processing starts with missing data management. After that, the texts are normalized by lowercasing the letters, handling special characters and missing values, and removing stopwords. Then, the words are tokenized, vectors and sequences are formed, and the dataset is split. The overall process is illustrated in Figure 1.

1. Dataset Description:

The Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI) dataset, prepared from social media posts, has been used in this paper. The sentiment of the posts has been classified into sixteen personality types, which are the combination of Extraversion/Introversion (EI), Sensing/Intuition (SI), Thinking/Feeling (TF), and Judging/Perceiving (JP) [20]. Table I presents a sample of the dataset.

2. Missing Data Management:

During the dataset analysis, several irrelevant instances have been discovered and removed. It introduced a missing value problem. The dataset is defined as a collection of text T where $T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_N\}$ with N entries. Some t_i might be missing. The replacement for any missing value t_{missing} is performed using equation 1 [21].

$$t'_i = \begin{cases} t_i, & \text{if } t_i \text{ is not missing} \\ \text{mode}(T) \text{ or } t_{\text{placeholder}}, & \text{if } t_i \text{ is missing} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

3. Normalizing the Texts:

The dataset has been normalized by converting the capital letters into small letters, as this variation does not contribute to the meaning but introduces complexities in the feature vector. The special characters and Uniform Resource Locators (URLs) have also been removed. Finally, the stop-words have been removed in the text normalization process [22].

a. Converting to Lowercase:

Every word defined by v_k in equation 2 is processed by the function $M:\text{String} \rightarrow \text{String}$. It converts any capital letter available in the world into a small letter. This process does not affect the meaning of the text. However, it simplifies the feature vectors [23].

$$M(v_k) = \text{lowercase}(v_k), \quad \forall k \in [1, m_i], \forall l \in [1, L] \quad (2)$$

c. Handling Special Characters and URLs:

The dataset analysis reveals the presence of special characters and URLs in the sample posts, which play no role in the sentiment of the text. As a result, they have been removed from the dataset. The removal process is governed by equation 3 where a bespoke function $F:\text{String} \rightarrow \text{String}$ has been implemented, with its operational logic delineated in the ensuing equation [24].

$$F(v_k) = \text{eliminate_elements}(v_k), \forall k \in [1, m_l], \forall l \in [1, L] \quad (3)$$

c. Removing Stopwords:

In an effort to streamline the feature space, stopwords were excluded from the MBTI dataset, effectively reducing feature dimensionality. Stopwords, which provide a minimal contribution to textual meaning and context, consist of commonly used words in English that detract from the analytical focus on critical elements. Recognized as a potent strategy for feature optimization in natural language processing, the exclusion of stopwords significantly enhances the analytical clarity of the dataset. The set comprising all identified stopwords in English is represented by R , and the function $F: \text{String} \rightarrow \text{String}$ s_i is defined to purge these stopwords from any text, as per equation 4 [25].

$$F(s_i) = [u_k \mid u_k \notin R], \quad \forall i \in [1, M] \quad (4)$$

The overall normalization process utilized in this study is described through a concise function, where M delineates the operation, and s_i is the i_{th} text sample. The overall process is expressed in equation 5.

$$M(s_i) = F(G(H(s_i))), \quad \forall i \in [1, M] \quad (5)$$

4. Tokenization:

The normalized dataset is ideal for tokenization, an essential step in processing the data for the proposed BiLSTM network. The given text sample S is dissected into an array of discrete elements, either words or subwords. This procedure is governed by equation 6, wherein ϕ denotes the tokenization operation [26].

$$\phi(S) = [s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n], \quad \forall n \leq m \quad (6)$$

5. Vectorization & Sequence Padding:

The BiLSTM networks require vectorized sequences of tokens to learn from the features of the MBTI dataset. In this paper, the token u and a corresponding word embedding ψ , each token gets associated with a vector within R^n , where n represents the embedding space's dimensionality. This relationship is articulated through equation 7 [27].

$$\psi(u) \in R^n \quad (7)$$

After forming the word vector, the text sequences are transformed into a sequence expressed as $\xi(S) = [u_1, u_2, \dots, u_m]$. The procedure for converting these sequences into a series of vectors accommodating multiple input tokens is defined by equation 8.

$$Z = [\psi(u_1), \psi(u_2), \dots, \psi(u_m)] \quad (8)$$

Given the variable lengths of vectors as presented in equation 8, a consistent input size is required for BiLSTM network functionality. This paper employs sequence padding to address discrepancies in vector lengths. Through this method, each vector sequence Z is either extended or shortened to a uniform length M , utilizing zero-padding vectors in R^n as per the equation 9 [28].

$$\text{Standardize}(Z, M) = \begin{cases} |z| \ll [0_{pad}, 0_{pad}, \dots], & \text{if } |z| < M \\ Z[1:M], & \text{if } |z| \geq M \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Figure 1: The flowchart of the dataset analysis and processing

6. Dataset Splitting:

The original MBTI dataset comprises 8675 entries. Following the dataset’s preparation, it consists of 8670 items. The division of the dataset for this study was into training, testing, and validation segments, with proportions of 70%, 15%, and 15%, respectively. The distribution across these subsets was achieved through a random selection process, ensuring considerable diversity within each group. Post-division, the dataset featured 6069 entries for training and 1300 entries each for testing and validation purposes [29].

TABLE 1: THE MBTI DATASET SAMPLE WITH EACH MBTI TYPE

User ID	MBTI Type	MBTI Type Full Form
User_1	INTJ	Introverted Intuitive Thinking Judging
User_2	INFJ	Introverted Intuitive Feeling Judging
User_3	ISTJ	Introverted Sensing Thinking Judging
User_4	ISTP	Introverted Sensing Thinking Perceiving
User_5	INTP	Introverted Intuitive Thinking Perceiving
User_6	INFP	Introverted Intuitive Feeling Perceiving
User_7	ENFJ	Extraverted Intuitive Feeling Judging
User_8	ENFP	Extraverted Intuitive Feeling Perceiving
User_9	ENTJ	Extraverted Intuitive Thinking Judging
User_10	ENTP	Extraverted Intuitive Thinking Perceiving
User_11	ESFJ	Extraverted Sensing Feeling Judging
User_12	ESFP	Extraverted Sensing Feeling Perceiving
User_13	ESTJ	Extraverted Sensing Thinking Judging
User_14	ESTP	Extraverted Sensing Thinking Perceiving
User_15	ISFJ	Introverted Sensing Feeling Judging
User_16	ISFP	Introverted Sensing Feeling Perceiving

B. D3Advert BiLSTM Network

A suitable BiLSTM network has been developed in this paper to build the D3Advert, which has been illustrated in figure 2. The MBTI dataset consists of sample posts with variable lengths. However, it has been observed that no sample exceeded 1500 characters. That is why the proposed BiLSTM network’s input character limit is 1500. After the input layer of the network, there is an embedding layer. It is responsible for generating 3D Tensor vectors [30]. The first dimension of this vector is the dimension of the embedding (E), the second dimension is the input limit (L), and the last dimension is the size of the batch (B). The LSTM layers of the network require 3D Tensors [31]. That is why the inputs are converted into 3D Tensors before sending them to the LSTM layer. The LSTM nodes of this layer extract the features, which are later passed to the global max pooling layer.

This layer reduces the feature vector size by selecting the most significant features. These features are then transmitted to the dense layer. The dense layer consists of 128 nodes. It has a fully connected architecture [32] with sixteen output nodes. The Softmax activation function has been used in this network to predict the classes [33].

1. Network Architecture Design:

The proposed BiLSTM network consists of a trio of gates that orchestrate the data flow: the forget gate (r_t), input gate (a_t), and output gate (s_t). These are defined in equations 10, 11, and 12, respectively.

$$r_t = \sigma(U_r \cdot [g_{t-1}, x_t] + c_r) \quad (10)$$

$$a_t = \sigma(U_a \cdot [g_{t-1}, x_t] + c_a) \quad (11)$$

$$s_t = \sigma(U_s \cdot [g_{t-1}, x_t] + c_s) \quad (12)$$

Here, r_t , a_t , and s_t represent the gates' activities at any given timestep, activated by a Sigmoid function σ . U_r , U_a , and U_s are the weight matrices, while c_r , c_a , and c_s are bias terms corresponding to each gate. The cell state G_t and the hidden state g_t dynamics, integral to both the forward and reverse flows of the BiLSTM layer, governed by equation 13.

$$G_t = \tanh(U_g \cdot [g_{t-1}, x_t] + c_g) \quad (13)$$

Updating these states hinges on the inputs received, which follows the mathematical principle expressed in equations 14 and 15.

$$G_t = r_t \cdot G_{t-1} + a_t \cdot G_t \quad (14)$$

$$g_t = s_t \cdot \tanh(G_t) \quad (15)$$

Bi-directional flow is key to BiLSTM's prowess, allowing information movement in both past-to-future and future-to-past directions. These flows are defined by equations 16 and 17, respectively.

$$g_t^f = LSTM_{\text{forward}}(g_{t-1}^f, x_t) \quad (16)$$

$$g_t^r = LSTM_{\text{reverse}}(g_{t+1}^r, x_t) \quad (17)$$

To synthesize the output from BiLSTM's dual pathways, an averaging strategy is employed, which is governed by equation 18.

$$g_t = \frac{g_t^f + g_t^r}{2} \quad (18)$$

Subsequent to the BiLSTM layer, a global maximum pooling layer condenses the vector sequences $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ into a singular vector Q , utilizing the method expressed in equation 19.

$$Q_j = \max_{i=1}^n (v_{i,j}) \quad (19)$$

The dense layer then processes Q as per equation 20.

TABLE 2: THE PROPOSED BiLSTM NETWORK SUMMARY WITH OPTIMAL

Parameter	Value
Number of BiLSTM Layers	3
Units in Each BiLSTM Layer	128
Activation Function	'tanh'
Dropout Rate	0.4
Recurrent Dropout Rate	0.2
Dense Layer Units	128
Dense Layer Activation	'relu'
Output Layer Activation	'softmax'
Optimizer	'Adam'
Learning Rate	0.001
Batch Size	32
Number of Epochs	15
Loss Function	'categorical_crossentropy'

$$= \phi \left(\sum_{i=1}^d (v_i \cdot u_i) + k \right) \quad (20)$$

Here, ϕ signifies the ReLU function, ensuring non-linear transformation which is defined by equation 21.

$$\phi(x) = \max(0, x) \quad (21)$$

Finally, to predict the MBTI traits, a sixteen-node output layer, utilizing a Sigmoid function for probability estimation, concludes the architecture, which is expressed in equation 22.

$$\phi(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}} \quad (22)$$

The network architecture summary of the proposed BiLSTM network has been presented in table II which shows the optimal parameters of the network.

2. Learning & Optimization Algorithm:

After processing the dataset, there are 8670 instances in the MBTI dataset, which varies in length. The mini-batch method has been used instead of using all instances together to ensure speed and efficiency during the training process. Each mini-batch consists of 800 instances, resulting in 10 mini-batches. The Adaptive Moment Estimation (ADAM) optimization algorithm has been used to optimize the weights of the proposed BiLSTM network [34].

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Figure 1: The proposed BiLSTM network’s learning progress with both accuracy and loss

Figure 2: The proposed BiLSTM network architecture to develop the D3Advert

a. Learning Curve:

The depicted learning trajectory in the referenced figure 3 illustrates the developmental stages of the BiLSTM network’s performance across training and evaluation phases, charting both precision metrics and error rates. This visual representation, delineated in figure 3(a), captures the fluctuation in accuracy for both training and validation phases, whereas figure 3(b) details the variations in error rates encountered during these phases. Initial stages are marked by pronounced fluctuations, highlighting a period of erratic learning.

This pattern persists until the completion of the fourth cycle. Subsequently, a noticeable transition to more consistent and nearly stable learning patterns emerges, indicative of the network's effective adaptation and learning. A particularly discernible aspect within these charts is the slight gap observed between the performance metrics of the training and validation phases, suggesting a well-balanced model that adeptly avoids the pitfalls of overfitting or underfitting.

b. Batch Normalization:

This paper employs the minibatch approach to enhance the training process's speed. It's crucial for each mini-batch to exhibit significant variance to avoid overfitting. Through batch normalization, this paper aims to normalize each mini-batch by minimizing its mean and maximizing its variance. A mini-batch, M , containing elements $(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{90})$ is defined by equation 23 [35].

$$M = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{90}\} \tag{23}$$

The mean (μ_M) and variance (σ_M^2) of the batch have been calculated using equations 24 and 25.

$$\mu_M = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \tag{24}$$

$$\sigma_M^2 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \mu_M)^2 \tag{25}$$

Normalization is then performed, adjusting each element in M using its mean and variance, with a small constant ϵ to ensure numerical stability. This process follows the mathematical procedure expressed in equation 26 [36].

$$\tilde{x}_i = \frac{x_i - \mu_M}{\sqrt{\sigma_M^2 + \epsilon}} \tag{26}$$

Finally, normalized values are adjusted through scaling (α) and shifting (β), which fine-tunes the learning process. The process is expressed using equation 27.

$$y_i = \alpha \tilde{x}_i + \beta \tag{27}$$

This sequence of steps, from normalization to scaling and shifting, ensures each mini-batch is optimally prepared for training, promoting a stable and efficient learning trajectory for the neural network model.

c. Optimization Algorithm

According to M. G. M. Abdolrasol et al. [37], the Adaptive Moment Estimation (ADAM) is a superior optimizer for training deep learning models. This effectiveness stems from integrating two distinct optimization techniques: Gradient Descent with Momentum (GDM) and Root-Mean-Square Propagation (RMSProp). ADAM's approach involves initial calculations of both the first and second order moments, defined by equations 28 and 29, respectively.

$$u_p^{(t+1)} = \gamma_1 u_p^{(t)} + (1 - \gamma_1) \nabla_p L(p) \tag{28}$$

$$v_p^{(t+1)} = \gamma_2 v_p^{(t)} + (1 - \gamma_2) \left(\nabla_p L(p) \right)^2 \tag{29}$$

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Bias correction plays a pivotal role in ADAM's optimization strategy, enhancing the accuracy of moment estimates. This correction adjusts the initially computed moments to refine the learning process using equations 30 and 31.

$$\widetilde{u}_p^{(t+1)} = \frac{u_p^{(t+1)}}{1 - \gamma_1^{(t+1)}} \quad (30)$$

$$\widetilde{v}_p^{(t+1)} = \frac{v_p^{(t+1)}}{1 - \gamma_2^{(t+1)}} \quad (31)$$

Leveraging these bias-corrected moments, ADAM adaptively updates the model weights, dynamically adjusting the learning rate based on the observed improvements using equation 32.

$$p^{(t+1)} = p^{(t)} - \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{\widetilde{v}_p^{(t+1)} + \delta}} \widetilde{u}_p^{(t+1)} \quad (32)$$

This sequence ensures ADAM optimizes the learning trajectory efficiently, dynamically adapting the weight adjustments for optimal model performance.

TABLE 2: THE PERFORMANCE VALIDATION THROUGH K-FOLD CROSS VALIDATION

k-fold	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
1	85.11	84.74	84.23	83.65
2	85.24	85.19	83.99	83.87
3	83.44	84.11	82.74	83.7
4	87.1	85.55	85.33	84.65
5	86.19	85.97	84.26	83.62
	85.416	85.112	84.11	83.898

C. Data-Driven Decision Making

The proposed data-driven decision-making system for ad personalization through personality analysis using the BiLSTM network is illustrated in figure 4. The process starts with the customer database query, where customers' information, including their social media profile URLs, is available. The query retrieves the social media profile of the target customer, and the profile URL goes to the Social Media Scraper. The scraper accesses the profile, retrieves the HTML page, inspects the tags, and stores the posts in arrays. These arrays are then transferred to the D3Advert Data Processing module. This module normalizes the text, tokenizes them, converts them into vectors, and performs sequence padding. After that, the vectorized word sequences are passed to the BiLSTM network. It predicts the personality. Based on this prediction, the advertisement is designed and delivered.

B. Confusion Matrix Analysis

The confusion matrix illustrated in figure 5 reveals the performance of the personality classifier in the context of the Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI) personality classification. High values along the diagonal suggest effective identification, particularly for ENFP, ESFP, and ISFP types, with correct predictions at 74, 75, and 68 respectively, and corresponding high classification accuracies, peaking at 90.7% for ISFP. Contrastingly, INTP and ISFJ show lower correct predictions, at 69 and 66, with the least classification accuracy for INTP at 78.4%. The precision range, from 76.2% for INFP to 93.8% for ESFP, reflects the frequency of correct predictions when a type is predicted. Misclassifications, evident in off diagonal values, such as ENFJ being mistaken for ENFP 4 times, suggest potential confusion between types with similar traits. This matrix illustrates the classifier's strengths and weaknesses across different personality types, indicating a generally good performance with specific areas for improvement, particularly in distinguishing between certain similar personality types.

C. k-Fold Cross Validation

The data presented in table III demonstrates consistent and robust performance across all metrics: accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. The accuracy scores across the five folds range narrowly from 83.44% to 87.1%, underscoring the model's reliability in correctly identifying personality classes. Precision, which reflects the model's correctness when predicting each class, also shows minimal variation, peaking at 85.97%, which is indicative of a high rate of true positive predictions across the folds. Recall scores, illustrating the model's ability to find all positive instances, hold steady above 82%, with a high of 85.33% in the fourth fold, suggesting consistent sensitivity across different subsets of the data. The F1-score, which balances precision and recall, remains above 83% for all individual folds, reinforcing the model's balanced performance.

Figure 5: Performance validation through k-fold cross validation

After aggregating, the average metrics, with an accuracy of 85.416%, precision of 85.112%, recall of 84.11%, and F1-score of 83.898%, demonstrate that the model's performance is not only high but also remarkably stable across different partitions of the data. The graphical illustration of the k-fold cross-validation in figure 6 agrees with this statement. This consistently high-performance level in all four measures confirms that the personality classification model is well tuned and generalizes effectively across the dataset, providing confidence in its use for predictive tasks within this domain.

D. D3Advert Experimental Performance Analysis

The proposed D3Advert has been experimented with in a test environment to analyze its performance. The test environment consists of five customers. They granted the permission to use their social media profiles. In the experiment's first phase, each customer's personality was predicted using the proposed system developed in this paper. Their personalities were identified by professional psychologists as well. They were given some generalized advertisements and requested to score the impression in percentage. Later, advertisements were personalized according to the predicted personality. Again, they evaluated the advertisements by scoring the impression. The performance of this experiment has been listed in table IV.

The efficacy of the innovative D3Advert system is convincingly demonstrated in the controlled experimental settings, as is evident from the performance data tabulated in Table IV.

In an impressive alignment with professional psychological assessments, the system precisely predicted the personalities of all five participants, a testament to its accuracy. The enhancement in advertisement effectiveness is unambiguous; personalized ads, which were crafted based on the system's predictions, saw a substantial increase in impression scores among the customers. For instance, Customer 1's impression leaped from a modest 30% to a striking 75%, while Customers 3 and 4 each observed a remarkable 45% surge in their impression scores. Such significant improvements, with an average rise of 40% across the board, emphatically affirm the system's capability to tailor content that resonates more profoundly with individual preferences. The D3Advert system not only validates the importance of personalized advertising but also proves its prowess in executing it with exceptional precision, thereby substantially enhancing the impact and effectiveness of the advertisements.

V. LIMITATION AND FUTURE SCOPE

The proposed D3Advert system suffers from several limitations. These limitations have been discussed in this section. However, instead of considering these limitations as drawbacks, they have been considered as the future scope of this research to conduct further experiments and overcome them.

A. Permission Dependent

The system requires the permission of the customers to analyze their social media profiles. If the permission is not granted, it goes beyond the legal boundaries of the proposed system [40]. It is a significant limitation of it. A well-defined user agreement with the assurance of privacy solves this problem. However, it has not been addressed in this paper and will be explored in the future scope of this research.

B. Post Length Limitation

The system fails to process social media posts with more than 1500 tokens. Although appropriate for the MBTI dataset, it may not be appropriate for all datasets. Sometimes, social media posts are longer than what 1500 tokens can accommodate. It is another limitation of the system. This limitation will be overcome in the subsequent version of the D3Advert.

C. Experimental Setup

The proposed D3Advert has been experimented with in a test environment. The customers in the test environment are not real customers. It is another major limitation of the paper. However, these dummy customers behave as real customers, which justifies the experimental analysis. Yet, a real-world performance analysis is essential, which will be explored in the future scope of this research.

The limitations of this paper pave the path to continue further research, improve the performance and capability of D3Advert, and make it a robust and efficient system for advertisement personalization.

VI. CONCLUSION

Advertisements tailored to the psychological profiles of individuals have been shown to outperform generalized ads, significantly enhancing the efficacy of advertising campaigns by elevating impressions and conversion rates. Nevertheless, the vast number of consumers makes it impractical for humans to ascertain each individual's personality. The introduction of a data-driven approach for ad personalization, utilizing personality analysis through a Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (BiLSTM) network, adeptly bridges this gap. This BiLSTM network, trained on an MBTI dataset compiled from social media activity, exhibits an admirable classification accuracy of 85.42%. The system also boasts commendable precision, recall, and F1-score values—85.11%, 84.11%, and 83.89%, respectively. Empirical analyses underscore that the system's predictions are in strong concordance with those made by professional psychologists. Furthermore, it has been observed that the system augments the impression rates of advertisements by an average of 40%. Despite facing certain manageable constraints, the D3Advert system's performance is remarkable, showcasing the transformative potential of personalized advertising in enhancing engagement and effectiveness.

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